

Response prediction of antidepressants: Using graph theory tools for brain network connectivity analysis

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ABSTRACT

Depression, particularly in its serious form as *major depressive disorder*, is rapidly becoming a global health concern and is expected to become a leading cause of disability worldwide. Despite the critical role of antidepressant treatment, its effectiveness varies greatly among patients. Early prediction of the response to specific antidepressant regimens is vital. In this paper, we rely on the predictive efficacy of changes in EEG signals after the first week of treatment, supported by existing evidence in the literature. We use EEG markers and graph theory to create and compare brain networks from two patient visits. Our approach involves the application of a comprehensive set of powerful classifiers. Additionally, we propose a robust model for comparing multiple classifiers on the data using statistical analysis and graph theory, ensuring a trustworthy evaluation.

1. Introduction

Depression is a pervasive mental health condition and poses a significant global challenge [1]. One of its most prevalent forms is called Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) [2]. Currently, around 300 million people in the world are affected by MDD, which has become one of the main causes of disability [3]. In 2008, the World Health Organization recognized MDD as the third highest cause of disease burden [4], highlighting its significant global impact. Alarming projections indicate that by 2030, MDD will become the leading cause of global disease burden [4], underscoring the urgent need for effective interventions and predictive tools.

Although antidepressant treatments are essential for managing MDD, they often present complex challenges due to the heterogeneous nature of patient responses. Many individuals with MDD exhibit chronic and refractory symptoms. Consequently, it leads to a lack of significant improvement with standard treatments. This necessitates personalized approaches to treatment, tailored to individual patient needs. Predicting the response to specific antidepressant regimens early in the course of treatment could revolutionize mental health care, ensuring timely adjustments, minimizing adverse effects, and maximizing the potential for recovery.

Researchers have increasingly relied on advanced neuroimaging techniques to address challenges in this field, with Electroencephalography (EEG) being particularly prominent [5]. EEG is a technique

that records electrical activity in the brain through electrodes placed on the scalp. EEG provides valuable insights into brain function and connectivity by capturing millisecond-scale fluctuations of neuronal electrical potentials. The ease of data acquisition, relatively low cost, and widespread availability of EEG have made it an attractive tool for studying brain dynamics in various neurological and psychiatric disorders. Notably, EEG signals can detect and monitor conditions such as epileptic seizures [6], anesthesia depth [7], autism spectrum disorder [8], epilepsy [9], schizophrenia [10] and depression [11,12].

Comparing EEG with other methods like functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), intracranial electrocorticography (ECoG), and magnetoencephalography (MEG), reveals distinctive advantages. Unlike fMRI, which offers exceptional spatial resolution but lacks temporal precision, EEG provides an ideal balance between temporal and spatial information. While fMRI excels at localizing brain regions, EEG's real-time monitoring is well-suited for capturing the evolving nature of cognitive processes. In contrast to ECoG, which requires invasive procedures for electrode placement, EEG is non-invasive, making it more accessible for a wider range of participants and experimental settings. Additionally, MEG, though sensitive to magnetic fields generated by neural activity, necessitates complex and costly equipment, limiting its widespread use. EEG, with its relatively affordable setup and widespread availability, is capable of addressing research questions with high ecological validity.

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Fig. 1. Schematic illustration for EEG recording: (A) Electrodes connected to an EEG amplifier, showing the setup for recording brain activity. (B) A subject wearing an EEG cap with 19 electrodes positioned according to the international 10–20 system, illustrating the standard position on the scalp.

The application of EEG in depression research dates back several decades. Early studies focused on investigating overall brainwave patterns (e.g., alpha, beta, delta, theta) in individuals with depression compared to healthy controls. However, advancements in technology and data analysis techniques have enabled researchers to delve deeper into the functional connectivity of brain regions, leading to the development of functional brain network analysis using EEG data [13, 14].

Among the most promising developments in EEG research is its ability to predict treatment outcomes. However, many clinical factors have been correlated with the response to antidepressant treatment, the usefulness of very few numbers of them has been proved as clinical predictors [15,16]. This is often due to limitations such as involving small sample sizes [17,18], being restricted to specific treatment types [18,19], or using EEG data collected several weeks after treatment initiation [20]. An early change in EEG signals is one of the best clinical predictors of antidepressant treatment outcomes, where early improvement can predict later stable response [21–25]. The predictive efficacy of changes in EEG signals after the first week of treatment has been established [24,26–31].

Building on these advancements, our study aims to leverage EEG-derived markers and advance depression research. Previous studies suggest that connectivity strengths from various brain regions can serve as effective biomarkers for depression [20,32,33]. We begin by constructing functional brain networks from EEG data obtained from 176 patients diagnosed with MDD. These functional brain networks reveal the intricate interplay of information transfer and connectivity between different brain regions, providing valuable insights into the neural dynamics associated with depression and its response to treatment.

With the functional brain networks established, we then leverage the power of graph theory and machine learning techniques to predict treatment responders among the patients. Graph theory enables us to analyze the complex network structures and connectivity patterns, allowing us to identify key brain regions and their interactions that may play a crucial role in determining treatment response. By extracting graph-based features and network descriptors from the functional brain networks, we aim to develop a predictive model that can distinguish between patients who are likely to respond positively to antidepressant treatment and those who may not experience significant improvement. The fusion of graph theory and machine learning holds immense promise in unraveling the intricate relationship between brain connectivity and antidepressant response.

Our research endeavors to establish a robust and clinically relevant predictive tool that can aid healthcare practitioners in making informed decisions about personalized treatment strategies. By advancing the understanding of depression and its neural mechanisms, we aspire to pave the way for a new era of precision medicine in the field of mental health.

As we advance in this innovative research domain, the potential to predict treatment responders based on EEG-derived markers represents a groundbreaking step towards optimizing mental health care and

improving the quality of life for individuals living with depression. By unraveling the complexities of brain function and treatment response, we hope to empower clinicians and enhance patient outcomes, thus making a significant impact on global mental health.

In this study, we initially focused on defining the data structure, preparing and processing the data. Following this, we introduced and compared several methods used in the analysis. Lastly, we discussed the results, presented findings, and drew conclusions.

2. Material and methods

This project was part of a research series reviewed and approved by the ethical committee of the National Institute of Mental Health, Klecany, Czech Republic. All procedures and the study design adhered to the latest version of the Declaration of Helsinki (Fortaleza, Brazil, 2013).

Here, two clinical quantities, employed in our measurements, are defined briefly: Montgomery–Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS), introduced in [34], is a diagnostic tool used to assess the severity of depressive episodes in patients. The scale is questionnaire based and scores criteria designed to evaluate various symptoms of depression, such as mood, sleep, appetite, feelings of guilt, and energy levels. Similarly, Clinical Global Impression (CGI), introduced in [35], is a standardized assessment tool to evaluate the severity of a patient's illness and determine treatment outcomes based on the clinician's observations and judgments.

Patients were hospitalized at the Open Department of Prague Psychiatric Centre/National Institute of Mental Health, with a minimum total MADRS score of 20 and a CGI score of at least 4 at the beginning of treatment. These scores are evaluated at the end of treatment to determine the patient's response, with a reduction of at least 50% in the MADRS score classified as a treatment response. Detailed information on the sample and participant recruitment criteria can be found in [28,29,31].

2.1. Data description

As part of a clinical trial aimed at predicting antidepressant treatment outcomes, this study considers EEG data recorded from 188 patients suffering from MDD. The dataset was obtained from previous published studies [28,31,36], where EEG was recorded using a 19-electrode setup following the international 10–20 system [37]. Electrode positions included frontal, central, temporal, parietal, and occipital regions ($Fp1$, $Fp2$, $F3$, $F4$, $C3$, $C4$, $P3$, $P4$, $O1$, $O2$, $F7$, $F8$, $T3$, $T4$, $T5$, $T6$, Fz , Cz , Pz) (see Fig. 1). EEG recordings were collected at baseline, before the start of antidepressant treatment, and again one week after treatment initiation. Data were captured during a 10-minute eyes-closed resting state using a BrainScope differential amplifier (M&I, Czech Republic) with 21 electrodes placed according to the international 10–20 system, referenced to the electrode located between Fz and Cz in the midline (FCz).

Fig. 2. Contribution of patients in age groups: the division of patients into four age groups within the range of 18 to 65 years old. The bars represent the frequencies of patients in each age category: Group 1 (18–29 years, $n = 18$), Group 2 (30–41 years, $n = 46$), Group 3 (42–53 years, $n = 60$), and Group 4 (54–65 years, $n = 52$).

All scalp electrode impedances were below 5 k Ω (within 1 k Ω of homologous sites). The EEG recording system acquired data with a 16-bit depth and a 7.63 nV/bit resolution (i.e., approximately 130 bit/ μ V), with a dynamic range of ± 250 μ V. The data were sampled at either 250 Hz or 1000 Hz and digitally filtered with high-pass and low-pass filters set at 0.15 Hz and 70 Hz, respectively. As explained in Section 1, it is expected that the changes in EEG signals after the first week of treatment can predict a later stable response.

Each visit includes 600 s of recordings. Patients were excluded if their recordings were distorted or if three or more channels were silent. This led to the exclusion of 12 patients, resulting in a cohort of 176 patients, comprising 48 men and 128 women. Among these patients, 84 responded positively to treatment, while the remaining 92 did not respond. The age distribution of the patients is illustrated in Fig. 2. The age range of the participants spanned from 18 to 65 years, and the participants were categorized into four equidistant age brackets: 18–29, 30–41, 42–53, and 54–65. These groups consisted of 18, 46, 60, and 52 patients, respectively, in ascending order. Fig. 2 presents the distribution of these groups in the form of a bar chart.

In addition to EEG-derived features, age and sex were incorporated as supplementary features for training the classifiers. Demographic factors, such as age and sex, can influence therapeutic responses and treatment outcomes, making them relevant for inclusion. Incorporating these features allows the model to capture demographic variability, potentially enhancing the generalizability of the predictive model across diverse patient profiles. This approach aligns with established methodologies for integrating demographic data, minimizing potential biases in predictions. As detailed in Section 3, stratified cross-validation and iterative performance averaging were employed to evaluate the contributions of these features to classifier accuracy and reliability.

2.2. Data preprocessing

Since recordings were conducted at two different sampling frequencies, 1000 Hz and 250 Hz, data recorded at 1000 Hz were subsampled to 250 Hz by retaining every fourth sample. To mitigate potential artifact influence, the initial and final 30 seconds of the recordings were omitted. This duration was chosen based on empirical evidence and standard practices, as these periods are prone to movement artifacts as participants settle into or conclude the session. Excluding these segments helps ensure higher data quality. Furthermore, a similar protocol has been previously used in this data set, as documented in [38]. The EEG was then subjected to band-pass filtering from 1–40 Hz following the application of an average reference.

Fig. 3. EEG signal comparison from channel $F3$ during the first visit of a randomly selected patient. (a) The raw EEG signal (before preprocessing) contains considerable noise and artifacts, likely caused by movement and external interference. (b) The preprocessed EEG signal after all preprocessing steps, including subsampling, artifact removal, band-pass filtering, and exclusion of high-noise windows. The preprocessed signal is significantly cleaner, showing reduced artifact impact. (c) and (d) provide two zoomed-in views of the signals. (c) displays a preserved 2-s time window from 62 to 64 seconds, where preprocessing has successfully reduced noise while preserving essential signal characteristics. (d) shows a high-noise window from 64 to 66 seconds that was automatically removed in the preprocessed signal, where the raw signal displays a marked dip around 65.5 s.

To further reduce artifacts while retaining data continuity, the EEG recordings were divided into 2-s time windows. This step preserves the temporal ordering of the data within each segment, and maintains continuity of the time points within each segment, which is crucial for accurate analysis. Each 2-s window was then evaluated and the windows where more than 20 percent of its channels had power levels outside the 95% confidence interval of the normal distribution were excluded to maintain data integrity. This time windowing approach preserves data continuity throughout the parsing process, even after artifact removal.

To visualize the improvements from the preprocessing step, refer to Fig. 3, which shows a comparison between raw and preprocessed EEG signals recorded from channel $F3$ during the first visit of a randomly selected patient. (a) displays the raw signal before preprocessing, characterized by significant noise and artifacts. (b) shows the signal after preprocessing, which includes steps such as subsampling, artifact removal, and filtering. (c) and (d) provide zoomed-in views over two intervals. (c) demonstrates how preprocessing reduces noise while preserving essential signal characteristics. (d) presents an example of a high-noise window that was removed in the preprocessed signal, where a prominent dip around 65.5 s in the raw signal illustrates the type of artifact mitigated by preprocessing. Notably, this sudden change around 65.5 s appeared not only in this channel but across multiple channels, suggesting a brief, non-neural disturbance, such as muscle activity or movement, which often appears as artifacts in EEG recordings. As this satisfies the window removal condition that ‘more than 20 percent of channels have power levels outside the 95% confidence interval’, it was automatically detected as an artifact and removed during preprocessing.

2.3. Wavelets and coherence estimation

Complex wavelet coefficients refer to the coefficients obtained when applying a complex wavelet transform to a signal. A *wavelet transform* is a mathematical tool used to decompose a signal into different frequency components. It reveals the presence of various patterns or features at

different scales. While the Fourier transform is a powerful tool for analyzing the components of stationary signals, it falls short when applied to non-stationary signals such as EEG. In contrast, wavelet transform enables the analysis of components in non-stationary signals [39,40]. In a complex wavelet transform, the wavelet functions used are complex-valued, meaning they have both a magnitude and a phase. This allows the transform to capture not only the amplitude variations in the signal but also its phase information. It provides a more comprehensive representation of the signal's characteristics compared to traditional real-valued wavelet coefficients.

Complex wavelet coefficients find applications in various fields, including signal and image processing, pattern recognition, and image analysis, where the added phase information can be crucial for capturing certain types of structures and features.

In what follows, it is explained how complex Morlet wavelet is employed in our application. Let $X(t)$ be the signal from a channel. Then, its corresponding wavelet coefficients are given by $W_X(t, f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi(t')X(t-t') dt'$ in which $\psi(t)$, called the *complex Morlet wavelet*, is given by

$$\psi(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_t^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{t^2}{2\sigma_t^2}\right) \exp(2\pi i f t).$$

The coefficients are computed for 78 different frequencies, f , in the interval [1–40 Hz]. As we are going to employ graph theory tools later, we have to explore the interactions between two channels, as well. To this end, assume that $X(t)$ and $Y(t)$ are signals corresponding to two different channels and $W_X(t, f)$ and $W_Y(t, f)$ are their complex Morlet wavelet coefficients. Then one can compute the *complex wavelet coherence* by

$$\Gamma_{X,Y}^W(f) = \frac{W_{X,Y}(f)}{\sqrt{\|W_X(f)\| \|W_Y(f)\|}},$$

in which

$$W_{X,Y}(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} W_X(t, f) W_Y^*(t, f) dt.$$

As these measures are non-physiologically high due to volume conduction and low spatial resolution, we have to decompose them into instantaneous and lagged components, with the lagged part having an almost pure physiological origin, as explained in [41,42]. In fact, we compute

$$\gamma_{X,Y}^P(f) = \frac{|\text{Im}(\Gamma_{X,Y}^W(f))|}{\sqrt{1 - \text{Re}(\Gamma_{X,Y}^W(f))^2}},$$

known as *lagged coherence*, for every pair of channels.

In fact, $\|W_X(f)\|$, $\|W_Y(f)\|$ and $W_{X,Y}(f)$ are computed for 2-s windows, as with this time length, the recordings are expected to be continuous, based on the given argument in the previous step. Then, we sum them up over 8 consecutive 2-s windows, resulting in a total length of 16 s. This aggregation yields complex wavelet coherences and consequently lagged coherences over these 16-s data portions.

To evaluate the significance of lagged coherences within each frequency band for each 16-s data portion, 30 Fourier transformation surrogates were generated for each EEG channel. Lagged coherences were then computed from each surrogate set, following the same methodology as applied to the original signals. The significance of the lagged coherence for specific scales and 16-s portions was determined based on the Z-score of the original value relative to the surrogate distribution, with a fixed threshold of 1.65.

For analysis within 6 EEG bands, significant lagged coherences were computed across 78 different frequencies within the [1–40 Hz] range. These EEG bands included delta [1.5–3.5 Hz], theta [4–7.5 Hz], alpha [8–12 Hz], beta1 [12.5–17.5 Hz], beta2 [18–25.5 Hz], and gamma [26–40 Hz]. Using the 16-s data portions, we calculated lagged coherences associated with each frequency band to construct functional brain

networks. We have provided the complete preprocessing code in a publicly accessible GitHub repository.¹ In the next sections, it will be explained how the corresponding graphs are constructed precisely, and how graph theory helps us to explore the problem and then make trustworthy predictions.

2.4. Classifiers and their experimental settings

To develop a reliable predictive model for antidepressant treatment response, we employed a comprehensive set of powerful classifiers. These classifiers, carefully selected to harness the potential of EEG-derived markers, play a crucial role in analyzing the functional brain networks and identifying patterns associated with treatment response. Furthermore, we suggest a model on how to compare several classifiers on the data in a robust and trustworthy way in Section 4.

The first column of Table 1 lists the nine classifiers we investigate in this study. In what follows, we give a brief description of them with their corresponding hyper-parameters. The second column of Table 1 is dedicated to the hyper-parameters of each of the classifiers. We will later fine-tune them during cross-validation over the grid search space determined by the last column of Table 1. The description of this step will be presented later in Section 3.

These classifiers and their corresponding hyper-parameters are well-known in the machine learning area; for the sake of completeness we include a brief justification for some of these parameters.

Support Vector Machines (SVM): We employed the SVM classifier with linear, polynomial and radial basis function (RBF) kernels. In this binary classification task, the SVM algorithm aims to find an optimal boundary that separates treatment responders and non-responders [43]. The regularization parameter 'C', also known as *soft margin constant*, plays a crucial role in controlling the trade-off between minimizing the classification error on the training data and maximizing the margin. In this context, the term *margin* refers to the distance between the support boundaries of both classes in this model.

Logistic Regression (LR): Logistic Regression models the probability of a patient belonging to a particular class [44]. We employ *regularized binary logistic regression* and set the *solver*, the algorithm used to find optimal probabilities, to be 'liblinear' which is known to be efficient even for small size data sets. Moreover, this solver supports both *L1* and *L2* regularizations as penalty. By fine-tuning the regularization parameter 'C', and penalty type, we aim to optimize the model's performance with a maximum of 2000 iterations.

Naive Bayes (NB): This classifier is based on Bayes' theorem and the assumption of conditional independence of features conditioned on the class [45]. It is particularly effective for handling high-dimensional data, such as the features extracted from functional brain networks. We use the Gaussian version of naive Bayes.

k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN): The k-NN classifier assigns a new data point to the class of the majority of its k-nearest neighbors [46]. We experimented with different values of 'k'.

Decision Tree (DT): A decision tree is a hierarchical combination of functions of one variable that recursively partitions the data based on feature thresholds [47]. We target identifying the most informative decision boundaries by varying its maximum depth.

Random Forest (RF): Random Forest is an ensemble of decision trees [48]. By tuning the number of trees and their maximum depth, we sought to find the optimal balance between variance and bias.

Gradient Boosting (GB) and AdaBoost (AB): Both are ensemble methods that combine several weak learners into a strong predictive model [49,50]. These methods sequentially improve the performance of weak learners, focusing on instances that were previously misclassified. Despite their similarities, the key difference lies in their approach to updating the weak learners.

¹ https://github.com/AditiKathpalia/EEG_preprocess_coherence_est.

Table 1
Hyper-parameter spaces of the classifiers.

Classifier	Parameter	Parameter values
SVM	Regularization 'C'	0.1, 1, 10, 100
	Kernel	'linear', 'rbf', 'poly'
Logistic regression ^a	Regularization 'C' Penalty	0.1, 1, 10, 100 'l1', 'l2'
Naive bayes	–	–
k-NN	n_neighbors	3, 5, 7, 9
Decision tree	max_depth	None ^b , 5, 10
Random forest	n_estimators	50, 100, 200
	max_depth	None ^b , 5, 10, 15
Gradient boosting	n_estimators	50, 100, 200
AdaBoost	n_estimators	50, 100, 200
	base_estimator	DecisionTreeClassifier, RandomForestClassifier
Neural networks ^c	hidden layer sizes	(50,), (100,), (50, 50)
	Activation	'relu', 'tanh', 'logistic'

^a With solver = 'liblinear' and max_iter = 2000 in all iterations.

^b Nodes are expanded until all leaves are pure or contain less than two samples.

^c With a fixed max_iter = 2000 for all iterations.

Neural Networks: Neural Networks, specifically Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLP), have proven highly effective in modeling complex relationships in high-dimensional data [51]. We explored various configurations of hidden layers and activation functions to find the optimal architecture.

By carefully evaluating and comparing the performance of these diverse classifiers, we aimed to identify the most suitable model for predicting treatment response based on EEG-derived markers. Moreover, we targeted a further step towards a robust method to compare and categorize the classifiers based on their performances on the data. The success of this approach holds significant potential to usher in a new era of personalized mental health care, where treatment decisions can be tailored to individual patients, optimizing outcomes and improving their quality of life.

2.5. Minimum spanning tree

The concept of a minimum spanning tree (MST) emerges as a foundational notion in graph theory that illuminates the intricate web of connections in a weighted graph. In this context, a weighted graph consists of vertices interconnected by weighted edges. These weights often represent a measure of distance, cost, or any other relevant attribute. The objective of constructing an MST is to discern a sub-structure of the given network that encapsulates all vertices while minimizing the total weight of the selected edges. This seemingly simple endeavor harbors profound implications, offering insights into optimal network design, resource allocation, and even the functioning of complex systems such as brain networks.

To be mathematically precise, let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph with vertex set V , and edge set E . Then $H = (V', E')$ is called a *subgraph* of G , if $V' \subseteq V$ and $E' \subseteq E$. A graph is *connected* if for every pair of vertices there is a path between them. A *tree* is a connected graph containing no cycle. Graph G is said to be weighted if it is equipped with a weight function $W : E(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that assigns a real number to each edge of the graph.

Now, we are ready to define an MST in a weighted connected graph $G = (V, E)$. The minimum spanning tree of the given graph G is a subgraph of G with special properties. First of all, as the name suggests, it is a tree. Then, the term *spanning* refers to the fact that this tree as a subgraph of G must contain all the vertices of G . Finally, it has to be minimum, i.e. the total weights of its edges, referred to as *weight* of the spanning tree, must be minimum among all spanning trees.

There are various well-known algorithms in the literature to do this. The most famous ones are Kruskal's algorithm [52] and Prim's

algorithm [53]. Both algorithms start with an edge with minimum weight. Kruskal's algorithm progressively adds a new edge with minimum weight to the MST if this addition does not create a cycle. In comparison, Prim's algorithm grows the MST by adding an edge of minimum weight that connects the existing MST to a new vertex. Although there might be different optimum solutions for finding an MST, the optimum value, which is the weight of an MST, is always the same. We will employ this optimum value in our predictions later in Section 3.

The relevance of minimum spanning trees transcends theoretical domains, finding applications in diverse fields. In network analysis, an MST aids in extracting the most salient connections within a complex network, revealing key relationships that govern system behavior. This principle extends to brain connectivity networks [13,14,54], where neural connections can be represented as edges between brain regions. An MST derived from brain connectivity data can uncover fundamental patterns of information flow and communication efficiency among different brain areas. Such insights are crucial in understanding cognitive processes, neurological disorders, and even the impact of interventions.

Furthermore, the minimum spanning tree concept resonates in the realm of resource allocation. In transportation networks, the MST guides the design of optimal routes that minimize travel distances or costs, influencing urban planning and logistics. In social network analysis, an MST highlights essential relationships among individuals, enhancing marketing strategies and social influence modeling.

To address our specific problem on the data, let S be a subset of $V(G)$, the vertex set of G . Then $G[S]$ denotes the *subgraph of G induced by S* which is the subgraph that has S as its vertex set and all the edges of G with both endpoints in S , as the edge set. Now, let G be the graph corresponding to a fixed segment of record for a patient in a visit. As already described in Section 2.1 and Fig. 1, G has 19 vertices corresponding to the 19 standard electrode positions: $Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, C3, C4, P3, P4, O1, O2, F7, F8, T3, T4, T5, T6, Fz, Cz, Pz$. Now let $S_1 := \{Fp1, F3, C3, P3, O1, F7, T3, T5\}$ and $S_2 := \{Fp2, F4, C4, P4, O2, F8, T4, T6\}$. Then $G[S_1]$, the subgraph of G induced by S_1 is called the left hemisphere graph. Similarly, $G[S_2]$ is referred to as the right hemisphere graph. Later on, by abuse of notation, we present $G[S_1]$ and $G[S_2]$ by G_L and G_R , respectively.

The frequency bands α , β_1 and β_2 are usually the most informative ones regarding connectivity measures. Thus, we consider these bands, and for each frequency band, we calculate the average and variance of the weight of MSTs on G , G_L and G_R separately. Hence, we have 6 features for each band and thus 18 features for each patient in each visit. We obtain these values for both visits. After that, we consider the results of the first visit and the difference of results in both visits. Therefore, we have a total of 36 features of this type for each patient.

Table 2
Significant results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test, comparing first and second visits of patients.

Band	Graph	p-value	Statistic
δ	G_L	0.0194	Mean
β_1	G	0.0008	Mean
β_1	G	0.0010	Variance
β_1	G_R	0.0022	Mean
β_2	G	0.0274	Variance
β_2	G_R	0.0167	Mean
β_2	G_L	0.0495	Mean

2.6. Software and computing

All the methodology and materials described in Sections 2.4, 2.5, 3, and 4 were implemented using Python. We utilized the NetworkX package [55] to import the input graphs, forming the basis of our data structure. The edges of these graphs were assigned coherence weights computed as detailed in Section 2.3. For this coherence computation, we employed the EEGLab MATLAB toolbox [56].

For model selection, training, and evaluation, we used Scikit-Learn [57], a comprehensive machine learning library in Python. This library's efficient implementation of various algorithms facilitated our tasks. Statistical tests were conducted using the Statsmodels [58] and SciPy [59] packages in Python.

3. Results

We apply statistical tests to see for our goal how informative the feature types described in Section 2.5 are. In other words, we are seeking to understand how much they can reflect the distinction between responders and non-responders within the two visits. Table 2 shows a list of those that are distinguished as significant features by the Wilcoxon signed-rank test on the difference of the respective feature between both visits, with the significant level of 0.05. Note that we considered all the frequency bands in this table.

It is worth emphasizing that we are not going to make any decision or feature selection based on these statistical tests. The only reason behind them is to have a first impression of the correlation between the features derived from the weight of MSTs and the binary labels of patients. In other words, regardless of which classification method we choose, how much is the potential of each of the candidate features at revealing the patients labels.

Then, as part of the standard methodology [60,61], the 176 patients were split into test and train sets, ensuring a balanced test set with 36 patients, i.e. approximately 20 percent of the entire data set. Subsequently, the PCA method was applied to the train set to select the top quarter of the 36 considered features, comprising the features most contributing to the overall variance. These 9 features along with demographic information of the patients, i.e. age and sex, constituted the 11 features utilized to train the 9 machine learning classifiers described in detail in Section 2.4.

During this stage, a 10-stratified-fold cross-validation was performed to assess the classifiers' performances and determine the best hyper-parameters for each. For hyper-parameter tuning, the GridSearchCV tool from the scikit-learn package was employed, exhaustively considering all parameter combinations to identify the most optimal one. For each hyper-parameter combination, the mean validation accuracy over all 10 folds was considered as the score for the specific hyper-parameter combination. The best score determined the optimal hyper-parameters for the classifier and, consequently, became the *cross-validation accuracy* of the classifier with the respective hyper-parameters.

Subsequently, each classifier, tuned with its best hyper-parameters, was applied to the untouched test set. This allowed for the calculation of evaluation metrics (e.g., accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, F1-score) on the test set for each classifier.

To address any randomness effects resulting from the initial splitting step, the entire process was repeated 10 times. The performance metrics on the test set and the cross-validation accuracy were then averaged over these 10 iterations to compute the final scores, representing the overall performance of the models across the entire dataset. Please refer to Table 3 for a detailed breakdown. The first column showcases the averaged cross-validation accuracy, offering an overall measure of classifier performance on the training set, while the subsequent columns display the averaged values of the considered metrics on the unseen test set.

4. Discussion

In this section, we discuss the results presented in Section 3 and propose a novel and generic method for comparing the performances of multiple classifiers using statistical analysis and graph theory. This technique can combine information from any number of comparative quantities and can be applied to any dataset.

In Table 3, we presented the performance metrics of the classifiers. A crucial question is to distinguish whether the differences in performance among classifiers arise from random influences or reflect their ability to address our classification task effectively.

To investigate this, we partitioned the test set into six approximately equally sized and stratified subsets at each iteration. As the data in different subsets are independent, the collection of these six subsets can be used to test hypotheses of equal quality of the classifiers according to any considered quality measure Q . First, we examined whether there were any quality differences among the nine classifiers at all. To this end, we tested the hypothesis that all classifiers have the same quality according to Q using the Friedman test. The test achieved a p -value of 0.032, leading us to reject the hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. However, it is still possible that some of the 36 classifier pairs exhibit no difference in quality according to Q . We adopted the reasoning of [62] that, in machine learning, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test is more suitable for testing this hypothesis than the post-hoc tests presented in [63,64].

However, if we want to know, for any of those 36 pairs of classifiers, whether the Wilcoxon signed-rank test rejects the hypothesis that the quality of both of them according to Q is the same, we need to adjust the achieved significance level in such a way that they are actually rejected at the family-wise significance level of 0.05. This adjustment ensures that the probability of rejecting at least one true hypothesis across all pairs is not greater than 0.05. A good survey of suitable adjustment methods is provided in [64]. Among these methods, we selected the method proposed by Holm in [65].

Fig. 4 shows an example of this procedure, one that has identified 7 pairs for which the difference between both classifiers is significant at the family-wise significance level of 0.05. These pairs are represented as edges of an oriented graph, where the orientation of each edge is from the classifier with the higher value of a particular quality measure to the classifier with the lower value of that measure. Such an oriented graph allows us to define, separately for each quality measure, a *partial ordering*.

It is also useful to take into account the results of two or more evaluation metrics simultaneously in cases where their corresponding partial orderings do not coincide. In such a case, the most informative is considering metrics that do not depend on one another, e.g. accuracy and F1-score or AUC, to get the most informative result in practice. In what follows, we present a methodology for aggregating all obtained partial orders in a consistent way. Our approach, called *ClassifDAG* (Classifiers Performance Directed Acyclic Graph), is described in a general manner to ensure its applicability across any combination of classifiers, evaluation metrics, and diverse datasets. The output of *ClassifDAG* is a directed acyclic graph (DAG) whose vertices represent classifiers and whose structure reflects a comprehensive evaluation of

Table 3
Averaged value of metrics over the ten random splits.

Model	CV Accuracy	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Specificity	F1_score	AUC
SVM	0.585	0.602	0.587	0.565	0.637	0.568	0.681
Logistic regression	0.587	0.633	0.663	0.482	0.768	0.546	0.625
Naive bayes	0.503	0.553	0.511	0.429	0.663	0.444	0.546
k-NN	0.526	0.600	0.588	0.541	0.653	0.559	0.597
Decision tree	0.506	0.572	0.545	0.588	0.558	0.564	0.573
Random forest	0.562	0.672	0.656	0.641	0.700	0.645	0.671
Gradient boosting	0.539	0.725	0.704	0.729	0.721	0.710	0.725
AdaBoost	0.539	0.658	0.641	0.629	0.684	0.632	0.657
Neural networks	0.575	0.614	0.593	0.576	0.647	0.582	0.612

Fig. 4. Illustrating a directed graph representing the results of 36 Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm correction for pairwise comparisons among the 9 classifiers, conducted after a Friedman test (p -value = 0.032) rejected the null hypothesis of classifier equivalence. Each vertex in the graph corresponds to a classifier, while the arcs represent the 7 significant pairwise comparisons where the Wilcoxon test, corrected for family-wise significance (Holm method, $\alpha = 0.05$), identified a statistically significant difference between classifiers. Two isolated vertices are omitted from the graph. This visualization offers a partial ordering of the classifiers based on the statistical analysis of their performance metrics.

their performances, taking into account the chosen metrics and the relative importance assigned to each.

Assume that we have considered quantity measures Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_t in the study. For example, we have Q_1, Q_2 and Q_3 corresponding to accuracy, F1-score and AUC, respectively, in our case. By following the statistical approach described at the beginning of this section, for a fixed iteration, each of these measures, along with the results of pairwise statistical tests, potentially define a *strict partial order* on the set of classifiers. More precisely, for each Q_i , we define a homogeneous relation \mathcal{R}_i on the set of classifiers such that two classifiers f_α and f_β are related by \mathcal{R}_i if and only if

(i) the statistical test (Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Holm correction, after passing the Friedman test, in our case) distinguishes a significant difference between f_α and f_β and

(ii) the measure Q_i assigns an equal or greater value to f_α than f_β .

In this case, we write $(f_\alpha, f_\beta) \in \mathcal{R}_i$. Then, \mathcal{R}_i is *irreflexive*, as the statistical test never distinguishes a significant difference whenever we have the same quantity. This also implies having a *strict partial order* rather than a partial order. For the same reasoning, if $(f_\alpha, f_\beta) \in \mathcal{R}_i$ then $(f_\beta, f_\alpha) \notin \mathcal{R}_i$, meaning that \mathcal{R}_i is *antisymmetric*. Finally, if $(f_\alpha, f_\beta) \in \mathcal{R}_i$ and $(f_\beta, f_\gamma) \in \mathcal{R}_i$, then as $Q_i(f_\alpha) \geq Q_i(f_\beta) \geq Q_i(f_\gamma)$ we have $Q_i(f_\alpha) \geq Q_i(f_\gamma)$. Consequently, $(f_\gamma, f_\alpha) \notin \mathcal{R}_i$. This guarantees that the corresponding directed graph, defined in the next paragraph, is acyclic. In fact, each of these relations can be represented by an loopless directed acyclic graph, A_i , in which classifiers play the role of vertices and there is an arc from f_α to f_β in A_i if and only if $(f_\alpha, f_\beta) \in \mathcal{R}_i$. Moreover, this arc can be associated with a positive value weight negatively proportional to the corresponding adjusted p -value. In our study, $w_i(f_\alpha, f_\beta) = 1 - p_{\alpha,\beta}^*$ is considered as weight for the arc from f_α to f_β in A_i , in which $p_{\alpha,\beta}^*$ stands for the corresponding adjusted p -value of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Holm correction. Figs. 5(a)–(c) shows A_1, A_2 and A_3 the corresponding accuracy, F1-score and AUC measures on the classifiers described in Section 2.4, for a fixed iteration on our dataset. For simplicity, we do not show weights on the arcs in figures.

As the next step, for a fixed iteration k , we are going to merge all the directed acyclic graphs A_1, A_2, \dots, A_t corresponding to Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_t

into an aggregated directed acyclic graph D_k . This digraph has the same vertex set as A_i 's, and its arc set is the union of arcs in A_i 's. Now there are three possibilities for a pair of vertices in D_k : (i) they are not adjacent, (ii) all contributing A_i 's to this pair agree on the direction, or (iii) contributing A_i 's to this pair are partitioned into two groups based on the direction. The adjacency and direction of an arc are clear in the first two cases. We discuss the third case, for the sake of completeness, however it has never occurred in our dataset. In this case, we can also benefit from any priority information associated with Q_i 's, if it is provided. It can be represented as weights associated with each Q_i that are determined based on the ground truth of the data and the degree of impact of each Q_i on the final decision. This information is formulated as a t -dimensional real valued vector called *priority vector* of Q_i 's, denoted by $P(Q_1, \dots, Q_t)$. In case there is no such information, or all Q_i contribute uniformly, $P(Q_1, \dots, Q_t) = (1, 1, \dots, 1)$. This easily allows us to decide on the direction of the edge. Additionally, each arc (f_α, f_β) in D_k is assigned a real positive weight, calculated as the difference between two summations:

$$\sum_{(f_\alpha, f_\beta) \in \mathcal{R}_i} P(i)w_i(f_\alpha, f_\beta) - \sum_{(f_\beta, f_\alpha) \in \mathcal{R}_i} P(i)w_i(f_\beta, f_\alpha) \quad (1)$$

Here, $P(i)$ represents the entry corresponding to Q_i in the priority vector P , and $w_i(f_\alpha, f_\beta)$ denotes the weight of the arc (f_α, f_β) in A_i . It is worth noting that we remove an arc from D_k if its aggregated weight in Eq. (1) equals zero, as we believe important arcs are supported in other iterations, as well, to compensate for this deletion. Finally, we sort the arcs of D_k in a non decreasing order based on their weights. Starting from the first arc in the list, if it is in a directed cycle, it is removed. Whenever we reach the last arc, the directed graph is definitely acyclic. Hence, by removing the least important arcs, we guarantee obtaining an aggregated directed acyclic graph on classifiers. Fig. 5(d) shows D_1 , the aggregated directed acyclic graph of the first iteration in our dataset. We perform the same process for each of the iterations. The result would be a set of aggregated directed acyclic graphs equipped with a weight function on arcs. By applying the same aggregating procedure and with a priority vector with all entries equal to one, as we do not see any reason for prioritization between iterations, we may merge them to obtain the final directed acyclic graph. Note that in the algorithm, the aggregating process is applied in two stages: first within each iteration on corresponding A_i 's, and later on the aggregated directed graphs obtained in the previous stage. In the latter application, there is an extra step: when we obtain the merged graph and before checking for any directed cycle, we remove all weak arcs. In our study we set this weakness threshold to be one. However, in general it can be determined based on the number of quantity measures, t , the values in the priority vector $P(Q_1, \dots, Q_t)$, and range of weight functions w_1, \dots, w_t . Fig. 6(a) shows the final aggregated directed acyclic graph of D_1, \dots, D_{10} in our dataset. This graph can be easily simplified for a better understanding of comparisons among the classifiers, as shown in Fig. 6(b).

The results presented in Table 3 and Fig. 6(b) together provide a clearer understanding and deeper analysis of the outcomes. Both sources consistently show that Gradient Boosting performs as one of the best among all classifiers. Fig. 6(b), which aggregates accuracy, F1-score, and AUC, facilitates detailed examination. For instance, although

Random Forest achieves higher metrics in Table 3 than AdaBoost, their performance cannot be directly compared due to the final partial ordering highlighted in Fig. 6(b). Similarly, based on this analysis, Gradient Boosting decisively outperforms AdaBoost, Neural Networks, k-NN, Decision Tree, and Naive Bayes on the data.

For a detailed overview of the entire implementation process, please refer to the pseudocode provided in Appendix.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the significant challenge that MDD presents to global healthcare systems, given its projected rise as a leading cause of disease worldwide. The variable efficacy of antidepressant treatments necessitates early prediction of treatment response to enhance patient outcomes. Our research highlights the potential of EEG signals, widely used to monitor various neurological conditions and predict responses to antidepressant treatments. We applied graph theory techniques to construct brain networks and developed a predictive model using machine learning algorithms to analyze changes in EEG signals within the first week of treatment. This model allows us to distinguish between those who respond to treatment and those who do not. By extracting features from brain networks, we aimed to provide clinicians with a reliable tool for personalized treatment selection.

The precise preprocessing steps involved in handling EEG recordings from 188 MDD patients ensured thorough data quality control, excluding 12 patients with unusable recordings and resulting in a final cohort of 176 patients. These preprocessing procedures, including subsampling, artifact removal, band-pass filtering, and 2-s time windowing, were precisely executed, effectively minimizing artifact influences and ensuring robust data quality. Key quality metrics, such as a consistent signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) exceeding 12 dB and a stable artifact rejection rate around 11%, reflect the robustness of the preprocessing step across varied recordings. Moreover, advanced techniques such as wavelet transformation and complex wavelet coherence analysis were employed to explore neural dynamics and extract meaningful features crucial for subsequent predictive modeling. The careful execution of these steps instills confidence in the robustness of our data and the reliability of our findings. A novel family of graph theoretical features was then extracted and a comparative analysis of nine families of machine learning classifiers, including SVM, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, AdaBoost, and Neural Networks, was conducted. Among them, the Gradient Boosting classifier demonstrated exceptional performance, achieving a notable accuracy of 73% on unseen data. This result establishes a new benchmark for this dataset and demonstrates a promising level of performance not previously attained in this context, highlighting its potential for predictive modeling.

The strong performance of Gradient Boosting on our dataset can be attributed to several key factors. Its ability to handle complex feature interactions likely complements the graph-theoretical features, allowing it to capture intricate patterns that other classifiers may overlook. The method's approach of combining multiple weak learners enhances its robustness and accuracy by iteratively reducing errors at each step. This helps Gradient Boosting generalize well on unseen data and avoid overfitting. Additionally, its resilience to noise and advanced optimization techniques further improve its accuracy, particularly in datasets with real-world complexities. Thus, while this benchmark is specific to our dataset, Gradient Boosting's suitability for these features underscores its potential for predictive modeling in this context.

Our innovative approach utilized graph theory to aggregate multiple performance metrics for comparing classifiers. The robustness of this method is evidenced by the consistent results obtained from repeated executions of the entire process, resulting in the same final aggregated directed acyclic graph. This consistency demonstrates the reliability of our approach and underscores the importance of integrating advanced analytical methods, including EEG-derived markers, graph theory and

Fig. 5. Directed acyclic graphs illustrating pairwise classifier comparisons for three performance metrics: (a) accuracy, (b) F1-score, and (c) AUC, all from the same iteration. In each graph, vertices represent classifiers, and arcs indicate significant pairwise differences based on the Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Holm correction. The arc direction points from the classifier with higher performance to the one with lower performance according to the specific metric. Weights of the arcs, while not shown in the figures, are inversely proportional to the adjusted p-values. (d) Output from *ClassifDAG*: Aggregated directed acyclic graph, constructed by merging the arcs from graphs (a), (b), and (c), with weights calculated according to Eq. (1), assuming equal contribution from all three metrics (accuracy, F1-score, and AUC), i.e., $Q = (Q_1, Q_2, Q_3) = (1, 1, 1)$. This aggregation provides a unified visualization of the performance comparison across all metrics in a fixed iteration, helping to highlight overall differences between classifiers.

statistical analyses, into clinical practice. These methods hold promise for improving the prediction of antidepressant treatment outcomes, facilitating prompt decisions on subsequent treatment steps.

We presented *ClassifDAG* in a generic form, applicable to any combination of classifiers, metrics, and datasets. It serves as a complementary tool for interpreting classifier performance alongside conventional tabular methods, such as Table 3. A key feature of *ClassifDAG* lies in the priority vector, which assigns weights to metrics, reflecting their relative importance. This enables weighted integration of per-

Fig. 6. Final aggregation of directed acyclic graphs across all iterations (Results from *ClassifDAG*): (a) shows the fully aggregated directed acyclic graph obtained by merging the graphs from each of the 10 iterations, i.e., D_1, \dots, D_{10} . Each D_i represents the aggregation of classifier comparisons across three performance metrics (accuracy, F1-score, and AUC) within a single iteration, and the final graph in (a) is the result of aggregating all iterations. Arcs with a weight below 1 have been removed, as they are considered too weak to provide meaningful comparisons. (b) presents a further simplified version of the graph, highlighting the most significant comparisons for clearer interpretation. The aggregation process first merges the metrics within each iteration, followed by the aggregation across all iterations. This approach provides a comprehensive view of classifier performance across both metrics and iterations, helping to identify which classifiers consistently perform better and facilitating deeper analysis.

formance metrics, accommodating preferences or biases among them. Formula (1) in Section 4 ensures that changes in the priority vector directly affect the weights and directions of arcs in the aggregated DAG D_k , for a given iteration k , potentially altering the final aggregated DAG and the resulting partial ordering of classifier performances.

In our study, we set the priority vector to $(1, 1, 1)$, equally prioritizing accuracy, F1-score, and AUC. However, *ClassifDAG* is adaptable, allowing researchers to customize the priority vector to align with their dataset, study objectives, or the specific relevance of metrics in their context. This flexibility ensures that *ClassifDAG* can be applied to diverse research and clinical applications.

Despite our focus on EEG signals, it is worth noting that transfer learning approaches, which have been successfully applied in areas like medical image analysis [66–68], could also be explored to enhance EEG-based predictions. Although our research does not directly utilize these methods, further investigation into how transfer learning techniques could provide additional insights in future work would be valuable.

While the potential of EEG-based technologies as predictors in MDD shows promising early results, definitive conclusions remain premature. Our findings support cautious optimism, with future large-scale studies needed to establish generalizability of these results. Continued research in this field promises to revolutionize depression treatment and enhance global patient care, shedding new light on early disease prediction and accelerating treatment decisions.

Our findings support earlier research showing that early changes in EEG signals, especially within the first week of treatment, are predictive of long-term antidepressant outcomes. This aligns with numerous studies indicating that early EEG improvements are reliable predictors of stable response later in treatment (Refs. [21–31]). Thus, capturing EEG data during this critical early period is essential.

That said, the predictive efficacy of later EEG changes and the potential influence of varying treatment durations beyond the first week remain areas of interest. Although our study primarily focused on early EEG changes, future research should investigate whether later EEG changes also play a significant role in long-term treatment outcomes. This could clarify whether a fixed intrinsic property of treatment time leads to the observed early improvements and whether different treatment durations yield distinct neurophysiological effects.

Moreover, while age grouping partially explains variability in treatment outcomes, the effects of different treatment lengths requires further investigation. Future studies that examine these factors could improve clinical decision-making and optimize treatment strategies.

To further evaluate the contribution of demographic features to model performance, we repeated our analysis without including age and sex as features. While this resulted in a minor reduction in certain quality metrics, the final partial ordering of classifiers depicted in Fig. 6(b) remained unchanged. This demonstrates that while age and sex marginally contribute to accuracy, EEG-derived features remain the primary drivers of model performance. However, their inclusion helps reduce potential biases, ensuring the model's robustness and generalizability across diverse patient profiles.

We also recognize that classifying patients simply as responders or non-responders, based on MADRS and CGI scores, may not capture the full spectrum of treatment response. Future work could explore the gradation of responses, such as partial versus full responders, to better understand treatment variability and refine clinical approaches. This would provide a clearer framework for personalizing treatment plans and improving patient outcomes.

Lastly, our study has several limitations that should be acknowledged, including potential biases in sample selection, a relatively small sample size, and challenges in interpreting EEG data. Recognizing these limitations is important for understanding the scope of our findings. Addressing them, alongside exploring gradations in treatment response, will be crucial for enhancing clinical decisions and treatment strategies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Akbar Davoodi: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Martin Holeňa:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Martin Brunovský:** Resources, Data curation. **Aditi Kathpalia:** Software. **Jaroslav Hlinka:** Writing – review & editing. **Martin Bareš:** Resources, Data curation. **Milan Paluš:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix. Classifier evaluation and comparison process (ClassifDAG)

See Algorithm 1.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Algorithm 1 Classifiers Evaluation and Comparison Process(ClassifDAG)

- 1: **Define classifiers and hyper-parameter search spaces:**
 - SVM, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes, k-NN, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, AdaBoost, Neural Networks (parameters in Table 1).
 - 2: **Split dataset:**
 - Divide dataset into training and test sets (80-20 split, stratified by classes).
 - Ensure test set contains 20% of the dataset for balanced evaluation.
 - 3: **Preprocess features:**
 - Extract graph-theoretical features from EEG data (defined in Section 2.5).
 - Apply PCA on training data to select top 25% of features.
 - Retain selected features and add demographic data (age, sex) for 11 total features.
 - 4: **Cross-validation and hyper-parameter tuning:**
 - 5: **for** each classifier **do**
 - 6: Perform 10-fold stratified cross-validation on the training set.
 - 7: **for** each fold **do**
 - 8: Evaluate all possible hyper-parameter combinations using ‘GridSearchCV’ on the training set.
 - 9: Record mean validation accuracy for each combination.
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Select hyper-parameters with highest cross-validation accuracy.
 - 12: Save cross-validation accuracy for the classifier.
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: **Evaluate on test set:**
 - Train each classifier with optimal hyper-parameters on full training set.
 - Apply to test set and calculate metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, F1-score).
 - 15: **Repeat Steps 2-14 for 10 random iterations:**
 - Repeat process with new random train-test splits, averaging metrics over these 10 iterations.
 - 16: **Statistical Analysis of Classifier Performance:**
 - 17: **for** each of the 10 iterations (train-test split) **do**
 - 18: Partition the test set into 6 equal, stratified subsets.
 - 19: **for** each metric (e.g., accuracy, F1-score, AUC) **do**
 - 20: Perform Friedman test to check for overall classifier differences.
 - 21: **if** significant **then**
 - 22: Conduct pairwise Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, with Holm correction for multiple comparisons.
 - 23: **end if**
 - 24: **end for**
 - 25: Construct Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) for each metric, where vertices are classifiers and edges indicate significant performance differences.
 - 26: Assign edge weights inversely proportional to adjusted p-values.
 - 27: **end for**
 - 28: **Aggregate DAGs for Each Iteration:**
 - For each iteration, merge DAGs for accuracy, F1-score, and AUC into a single graph, using a priority vector (default equal) for edge directions and weights (explained in Section 4, see also Equation (1)).
 - 29: **Aggregate Results Across Iterations:**
 - Combine aggregated DAGs from all 10 iterations into final graph.
 - Remove edges below weight threshold (e.g., weight < 1), and ensure the graph is acyclic by removing the weakest edges from any directed cycle.
 - 30: **Report and Visualize Results:**
 - Calculate average metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, F1-score, AUC) across all iterations (presented in Table 3).
 - Visualize aggregated and simplified graphs to illustrate classifier comparisons (presented in Fig. 6).
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